

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF SCHOOL TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE TO INTERACT WITH CHILDREN OF DEVIANT BEHAVIOR⁴

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the analysis of psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of professional competence of school teachers to interact with children with deviant behavior. The work examines the relevance of the problem of deviant behavior among schoolchildren, in particular, the phenomenon of bullying as one of its common forms. The results of teachers' survey presented in the work are aimed at studying their awareness of bullying, prevalence of this phenomenon in the educational environment, as well as approaches to its prevention and correction. Various aspects of the problem are analyzed, including forms of bullying, its causes, signs, and the reaction of teachers to cases of harassment. Special attention is paid to the need to train teachers in bullying management skills and the importance of involving school psychologists and social educators in effectively addressing the problem. Based on the data obtained, scientifically grounded recommendations are developed for educational institutions to improve the effectiveness of teachers' interaction with children with deviant behavior, aimed at creating a favorable and safe educational environment for all students.

Keywords: deviant behavior, bullying, teachers' professional competence, psychological and pedagogical conditions, prevention, correction, educational environment, survey.

In the contemporary society, the issue of deviant behavior among children and adolescents is increasingly acute and demands heightened attention from educational institutions. Deviant behavior, manifesting itself in various forms of aggression and violations of social norms and rules, not only negatively impacts children themselves but also the overall educational environment. Consequently, the professional competence of school teachers to effectively interact with children exhibiting deviant behavior becomes a pivotal factor in the successful socialization and adaptation of such students.

The study of psychological and pedagogical conditions that foster the development of this competence is particularly topical. A teacher working with children exhibiting deviant behavior must possess not only a profound understanding of pedagogy and psychology but also the ability to apply this knowledge practically, considering each child's unique characteristics. This necessitates a high degree of empathy, patience, capacity to establish trusting relationships, and an ability to devise constructive solutions to conflict situations.

The aim of this study is to formulate evidence-based recommendations for educational institutions to enhance the efficacy of teachers' interactions with children exhibiting deviant behavior, thereby facilitating

the creation of a conducive and secure educational milieu for all students.

Analyzing the current state of the interaction between school teachers and children with deviant behavior necessitates the consideration of numerous factors, including social, psychological, and educational aspects, as well as evolving pedagogical approaches. The problem's current state can be examined through several key dimensions, using bullying as an illustrative example.

Bullying is any unwanted or aggressive behavior from someone who is intentionally trying to upset, harm, or have power over another person [1].

There are numerous types of bullying, including verbal, physical, social, and cyberbullying. Harassment can be considered a form of bullying. But while harassment targets someone based on traits like race or gender and is often illegal, bullying is typically about power and isn't always protected by discrimination laws [2].

Bullies gain power by inciting a reaction out of others. To deal with a bully, one should stay calm and maintain control of his emotions, find a support system, and document the bullying as much as possible, for example, by taking screenshots of cyberbullying, and photographs of any injuries [3].

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Bullying in the educational environment is a pressing issue that concerns both students and teachers. To analyze awareness, forms of manifestation, causes, and

approaches to solving this problem, a survey was conducted. Below is a detailed analysis of the responses from the survey participants, conducted through the TypeForm platform, and recommendations.

Pic. 1. Awareness of bullying.

1. Awareness of bullying

The participants' complete awareness of the concept of bullying indicates that the topic is actively discussed in the society. However, it is important to ensure

that this knowledge is accompanied by an understanding of mechanisms of bullying and ways to prevent it.

Pic. 2. Different types of bullying

2. The most common form of bullying [4]

Verbal and social bullying (44.4%) are equally often perceived as the most common forms, which confirms their significance. At the same time, cyberbullying, which received only 11.1%, may be underestimated due to the difficulty of tracking and recognizing it.

According to researchers, verbal bullying, i.e., insults, threats, and disrespectful comments, is more common in Kazakhstan.

The Constitution of Kazakhstan states “Human dignity is inviolable: no one shall be subjected to torture, violence, or other cruel or degrading treatment or punishment” [5].

3. Signs indicating harassment

Teachers recognize that bullying affects a child in several aspects, including behavior, health, and academic performance. This understanding is important for timely intervention.

4. Main causes of bullying

Pic. 3. Main causes of bullying

Respondents consider peer pressure and children's lack of effective communication skills to be the main causes of bullying. This underscores the importance of preventive work in student groups.

5. Experience of encountering bullying

Most have witnessed bullying from the sidelines, which speaks to the prevalence of this phenomenon. However, the role of passive observers requires special attention, as their inaction can exacerbate harassment [6].

6. Reaction to a student's complaint about harassment

Almost half of the participants (44.4%) are ready to intervene personally, while a significant portion would prefer to refer the problem to the administration. This may indicate a lack of confidence or skills to independently resolve such situations.

7. Bullying of teachers by students

Some participants recognize bullying of teachers as a real problem, although it is considered a relatively rare occurrence. Nevertheless, even rare cases can lead to professional burnout and reduced motivation of teachers.

8. Bullying among employees

A significant number of people note that bullying among employees occurs, although it is not always perceived as a serious problem. This emphasizes the need to create a psychologically comfortable work environment.

9. Frequency of discussing bullying with students

Most teachers actively discuss the problem of bullying. However, it is important that these discussions are transformed into actions aimed at preventing bullying and teaching children skills to resist it.

Pic. 4. Frequency of discussing bullying with students

10. Teacher training in anti-bullying skills

Pic. 5. Teacher training in anti-bullying skills

Most participants (90%) recognize the importance of training teachers in bullying management. This indicates a high competence and professional development in this area. However, a minority (10%) consider it only an additional tool, which emphasizes the need to promulgate such programs.

11. Preferred approach to resolving bullying cases

Group work and discussion of the problem are the most popular approaches (40%), which confirms the importance of collective problem-solving. 30% prefer individual work, emphasizing that each case is unique.

12. Involvement of a school psychologist or social pedagogue

Most (60%) believe that a psychologist should be involved at initial stages, which demonstrates an understanding of the importance of timely intervention. However, 20% are willing to involve specialists only in critical situations, which may indicate a lack of resources. Teachers' responses show:

- 33.3% believe that the best way is to seek help;
- 26.7% noted the complexity of the situation;
- 20% are confident that support from friends and adults is needed.

These data highlight the importance of support for victims of bullying and the need to create a safe educational space for them.

The conducted research has revealed key aspects of the bullying problem within the educational environment, as well as assessed educators' competence to address it. The analysis of survey results indicated that, despite a high level of awareness regarding the phenomenon of bullying, there is a necessity for a deeper understanding of its mechanisms and effective counteraction methods [7].

The research also demonstrates that the majority of educators are willing to actively discuss the issue of bullying with students and recognize the importance of training in bullying management skills. However, to realize these intentions, it is necessary to create conditions for educators' professional development and implement relevant educational programs.

In conclusion, this research underscores the necessity of a systematic and multifaceted approach to addressing the problem of bullying in the educational environment. Creating a safe and supportive learning space requires not only enhancing educators' awareness and professional competence but also active engagement of students, parents, and specialists.

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